

INVERSE SCATTERING PROBLEM FOR A SYSTEM OF EQUATIONS DIRAC ON THE WHOLE LINE

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Abstract

In this paper, we study the inverse scattering problem for the Dirac operator on the whole line with real continuous coefficients $p(x)$ and $q(x)$, which tend to zero $x \rightarrow \infty$ rather quickly as and the Dirac operator with these coefficients considered on the semiaxis $(-\infty, a]$ has a purely discrete spectrum. For the Dirac operator under consideration, the S -function is introduced, its properties are studied, the Gelfand–Levitan–Marchenko integral equation is derived, and the procedure for restoring the coefficients $p(x)$ and $q(x)$ is given.

Keywords: Dirac operator, Jost function, Weyl solution, Weil–Titchmarsh function, potential matrix function, inverse scattering problem, S -function, spectrum, analytic function, Gelfand–Levitan–Marchenko integral equation, meromorphic function, spectral function, Gelfand–Levitan method.

INTRODUCTION

The following operators are called respectively the Sturm–Liouville (Schrödinger) and Dirac operators

$$L \equiv -\frac{d^2}{dx^2} + q(x), \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \quad (1)$$

$$D \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \frac{d}{dx} + \begin{pmatrix} p(x) & q(x) \\ q(x) & -p(x) \end{pmatrix}, \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (2)$$

are widely used in both mathematics and physics.

In the case of the Sturm–Liouville operator, the function $q(x)$, and in the case of the Dirac operator, the function $u(x) = q(x) - ip(x)$ called potential.

Finding the spectral characteristics of these operators from a given potential is called the direct problem, restoring the potential from some spectral characteristics is called the inverse problem for these operators.

The Dirac equation is one of the basic equations of quantum mechanics. It is obtained by factorization of the Schrödinger equation and describes some phenomena that cannot be explained using the Schrödinger equation. The Dirac operator, generally speaking, is not semibounded, and many of the methods developed for the study of semibounded operators are not applicable to it.

The inverse problem of scattering theory for the Sturm–Liouville operator in the class of potentials satisfying the conditions

$$\int_{-\infty}^0 (1-x)|q(x)| dx < \infty, \quad \int_0^{\infty} (1+x)|q(x) - c^2| dx < \infty,$$

well studied in the works of V.S. Buslaev, V.L. Fomin [1] and A. Kohen [2].

The next important step in this topic was made by P.P. Kulish [3], more precisely, he solved the inverse scattering problem for the Sturm–Liouville equation

$$-y'' + q(x)y = \lambda y, \quad (3)$$

with a potential that satisfies the following conditions

$$q(x) \rightarrow \infty, \quad x \rightarrow -\infty; \quad \int_0^{\infty} (1+x)|q(x)| dx < \infty. \quad (4)$$

In this case, the Sturm–Liouville equation (3) has a solution $u(x, k)$, having the asymptotics

$$u(x, k) = o(1), \quad x \rightarrow -\infty;$$

$$u(x, k) = S(k)e^{ikx} - e^{-ikx} + o(1), \quad x \rightarrow \infty,$$

where $k = \sqrt{\lambda}$.

Function $S(k)$ is called the scattering function for problem (3), (4). The inverse problem is to restore $q(x)$ according to a given function $S(k)$.

MAIN RESULTS

This article considers the inverse scattering problem for the Dirac operator (2), whose coefficients satisfy the following conditions:

(a) for any real finite a

$$|p(x)| \leq \frac{C}{(1+|x|)^{2+\varepsilon}}, \quad |q(x)| \leq \frac{C}{(1+|x|)^{1+\varepsilon}}, \quad x \in [a, \infty), \tag{5}$$

where $C > 0$, $\varepsilon > 0$ —constant numbers;

(b) spectrum of the problem

$$\begin{cases} Dy = \lambda y, & -\infty < x < a, \\ y_1(a) = 0 \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

discrete.

Consider the following system of Dirac equations on the whole line

$$Dy \equiv B \frac{dy}{dx} + \Omega(x)y = \lambda y, \quad -\infty < x < \infty, \tag{7}$$

where

$$y = \begin{pmatrix} y_1(x) \\ y_2(x) \end{pmatrix}, \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \Omega(x) = \begin{pmatrix} p(x) & q(x) \\ q(x) & -p(x) \end{pmatrix},$$

$p(x)$ and $q(x)$ —real continuous functions satisfying conditions (5), (6).

Denote by $\theta(x, \lambda)$ and $\varphi(x, \lambda)$ solutions of equation (7) satisfying the following initial conditions

$$\theta(a, \lambda) = (1, 0)^T, \quad \varphi(a, \lambda) = (0, -1)^T.$$

Weyl solution $\tilde{\psi}(x, \lambda)$ for problem (6) is uniquely determined by the condition

$$\tilde{\psi}(x, \lambda) = \theta(x, \lambda) + m_-(\lambda)\varphi(x, \lambda) \in L^2_2(-\infty, a),$$

where λ does not belong to the spectrum of problem (6). Function $m_-(\lambda)$ is called the function Weil–Titchmarsh for problem (6). Singular points of a function $m_-(\lambda)$ form the spectrum of problem (6), while the eigenvalues are simple poles of the function $m_-(\lambda)$. Here and further through $L^2_2(\alpha, \beta)$ denoted space vector–functions of two components, the square of the modulus of which is summable on the interval (α, β) .

Lemma 1. Under assumption (b), the function Weil–Titchmarsh $m_-(\lambda)$ represent in the following form

$$m_-(\lambda) = \frac{a_1(\lambda)}{a_2(\lambda)}, \tag{8}$$

where $a_1(\lambda)$ and $a_2(\lambda)$ entire functions that do not have common zeros (the zeros $a_1(\lambda)$ and $a_2(\lambda)$ alternate) and take real values at $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^1$; moreover, the zeros $a_2(\lambda)$ are simple and coincide with the eigenvalues of problem (6).

Proof. By assumption (b), the spectrum of problem (6) is discrete. Hence, the singular points of the Weil–Titchmarsh function $m_-(\lambda)$ consist only of simple poles. Then $m_-(\lambda)$ is represented in the form (8). Moreover, the zeros $a_2(\lambda)$ are simple and coincide with the eigenvalues λ_n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ of problem (6).

The functions $a_1(\lambda)$ and $a_2(\lambda)$ take real values for $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^1$. This assertion follows from the fact that the function $m_-(\lambda)$ takes real values at the real points of continuity. **Lemma 1 is proved.**

Theorem 1. Under assumption (b), there exists a nonzero solution $\psi(x, \lambda) \in L_2^2(-\infty, a)$, $\lambda \in \square$ equation (7), satisfying the following conditions:

- 1) $\psi(x, \lambda)$ is an integer vector-function relative to λ for every fixed $x \in \square^1$;
- 2) at $\lambda \in \square^1$, the components $\psi(x, \lambda)$ take real values.

Proof. Let $m_-(\lambda) = \frac{a_1(\lambda)}{a_2(\lambda)}$ and $\tilde{\psi}(x, \lambda)$ be the Weyl-Titchmarsh function and the Weyl solution for problem (6), respectively.

Let's put

$$\psi(x, \lambda) = a_2(\lambda)\tilde{\psi}(x, \lambda).$$

It's obvious that

$$\psi(x, \lambda) \in L_2^2(-\infty, a) \text{ at } \lambda \neq \lambda_k, k \in \square.$$

From the definition of the Weyl solution $\tilde{\psi}(x, \lambda)$, we find

$$\psi(x, \lambda) = a_2(\lambda)\theta(x, \lambda) + a_1(\lambda)\varphi(x, \lambda). \quad (9)$$

This implies that $\psi(x, \lambda)$ is an entire vector function with respect λ to fixed $x \in \square^1$. Since $\varphi(x, \lambda_k)$ it is eigenvector function of problem (6), then according to (9) we have

$$\psi(x, \lambda_k) = a_1(\lambda_k)\varphi(x, \lambda_k) \in L_2^2(-\infty, a), k \in \square.$$

So, $\psi(x, \lambda) \in L_2^2(-\infty, a)$ for any $\lambda \in \square$. On the other hand, considering

$$\psi(a, \lambda) = a_2(\lambda)\theta(a, \lambda) + a_1(\lambda)\varphi(a, \lambda) = (a_2(\lambda), -a_1(\lambda))^T \neq 0,$$

we get $\psi(x, \lambda) \neq 0$. **Theorem 1 is proved.**

Solution of system (7) satisfying the following asymptotics

$$f(x, \lambda) = \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x} + o(1), \quad x \rightarrow +\infty \quad (\text{Im } \lambda = 0),$$

is called the Jost solution. Under condition (a), the Jost solution exists, is unique, and can be represented as

$$f(x, \lambda) = \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x} + \int_x^\infty A(x, t) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda t} dt, \quad (10)$$

where is the core

$$A(x, t) = \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}(x, t) & A_{12}(x, t) \\ A_{21}(x, t) & A_{22}(x, t) \end{pmatrix}$$

does not depend on λ and satisfies the following conditions:

- 1) $BA'_x(x, t) + A'_t(x, t)B = -\Omega(x)A(x, t)$,
- 2) $BA(x, x) - A(x, x)B = \Omega(x)$,

$$3) |A_{ij}(x, t)| \leq \frac{C_1}{(1+|x|)(1+|t|)^{1+\varepsilon}}, \quad i \neq j,$$

$$|A_{ij}(x, t)| \leq \frac{C_1}{(1+|t|)^{1+\varepsilon}}, \quad i = j.$$

Where $C_1 > 0$ and $\varepsilon > 0$ – constantas.

The following lemmas are easily proved (see, for example, [4–6]).

Lemma 2. The solution $f(x, \lambda)$ can be continued analytically with respect to λ the half-plane $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$, and this analytical continuation is continuous with respect to λ in $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$, in addition, the following asymptotic formula holds:

$$f(x, \lambda) = \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x} \left[1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right], \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \text{Im } \lambda \geq 0. \tag{11}$$

Lemma 3. For $\lambda \in \square^1$, the vector function $\overline{f(x, \lambda)}$ is a solution to system (7) and the equality

$$W\{f(x, \lambda), \overline{f(x, \lambda)}\} = 2i,$$

that is $f(x, \lambda)$ and $\overline{f(x, \lambda)}$ constitute the fundamental system of solutions to equations. (7).

Here and below, $W\{f, g\} = f_1g_2 - f_2g_1$ we denote the Wronskian of vector functions f and g .

Lemma 4. If conditions (a) and (b) are satisfied, then for $\lambda \in \square^1$, the expansion

$$\psi(x, \lambda) = \frac{1}{2i} \overline{W(\lambda)} f(x, \lambda) - \frac{1}{2i} W(\lambda) \overline{f(x, \lambda)}, \tag{12}$$

where $W(\lambda) = W\{\psi(x, \lambda), f(x, \lambda)\}$, $f(x, \lambda)$ is the Jost solution of equation (7) and $\psi(x, \lambda)$ is the solution of equation (7) introduced in Theorem 1.

Proof. Since $\lambda \in \square^1$ for the functions $f(x, \lambda)$ and $\overline{f(x, \lambda)}$ they constitute the fundamental system of solutions to equation (7), there is an expansion

$$\psi(x, \lambda) = a(\lambda) f(x, \lambda) + b(\lambda) \overline{f(x, \lambda)}. \tag{13}$$

Using this expansion, we have

$$\begin{aligned} W(\lambda) &= W\{\psi(x, \lambda), f(x, \lambda)\} = W\{a(\lambda) f(x, \lambda) + b(\lambda) \overline{f(x, \lambda)}, f(x, \lambda)\} = \\ &= a(\lambda) W\{f(x, \lambda), f(x, \lambda)\} + b(\lambda) W\{\overline{f(x, \lambda)}, f(x, \lambda)\} = -2ib(\lambda), \end{aligned}$$

from here $b(\lambda) = -\frac{1}{2i} W(\lambda)$. Using the validity $\psi(x, \lambda)$ of at $\lambda \in \square^1$, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{W(\lambda)} &= W\{\overline{\psi(x, \lambda)}, \overline{f(x, \lambda)}\} = W\{\overline{\psi(x, \lambda)}, \overline{f(x, \lambda)}\} = \\ &= W\{a(\lambda) f(x, \lambda) + b(\lambda) \overline{f(x, \lambda)}, \overline{f(x, \lambda)}\} = 2ia(\lambda), \end{aligned}$$

$$a(\lambda) = \frac{1}{2i} \overline{W(\lambda)}.$$

Substituting into equality (13), the obtained expressions for $a(\lambda)$ and $b(\lambda)$ we derive expansion (12).

Lemma 4 is proved.

Lemma 5. Let conditions (a) and (b) be satisfied. Then:

- 1) $W(\lambda)$ is an analytic function in the half-plane $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$;
- 2) $W(\lambda)$ continuous in the half-plane $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$;
- 3) $W(\lambda)$ has no zeros in the half-plane $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$.

Proof. The first assertion of this lemma follows from the analyticity with respect λ to the functions $\psi(x, \lambda)$ and $f(x, \lambda)$, respectively, on the whole plane $\square$ and on $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$.

The second assertion follows from the continuity $f(x, \lambda)$ in the half- plane $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$.

Let's assume that $\text{Im } \lambda_0 > 0$ and $W(\lambda_0) = 0$. Then

$$\psi(x, \lambda_0) = \text{const} \cdot f(x, \lambda_0) \in L_2^2(a, \infty).$$

In force $\psi(x, \lambda_0) \in L_2^2(-\infty, a)$ we get that $\psi(x, \lambda_0) \in L_2^2(-\infty, \infty)$. Since $\psi(x, \lambda_0) \neq 0$, then $\psi(x, \lambda_0)$ is an eigenvector function of problem (7). This assertion contradicts the self-adjointness of problem (7) (see [7], p. 297).

In $\square^1$ the function $W(\lambda)$ does not vanish, since problem (7) has no eigenvalues. **Lemma 5 is proved.**

Let $\lambda \in \square^1$ and conditions (a) and (b) be satisfied. Let us divide both

parts of equality (12) by $\frac{1}{2i}W(\lambda)$. Then

$$u(x, \lambda) = S(\lambda) f(x, \lambda) - \overline{f(x, \lambda)}, \quad (14)$$

where

$$u(x, \lambda) = \frac{2i}{W(\lambda)} \psi(x, \lambda) \quad S(\lambda) = \frac{\overline{W(\lambda)}}{W(\lambda)}$$

The function $S(\lambda)$ is called the scattering function of problem (7). It is easy to see that $|S(\lambda)| = 1$.

Let's introduce the following function

$$S_0(\lambda) = e^{-2ia\lambda} \cdot \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda) + i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}. \quad (15)$$

Theorem 2. Let condition (b) be satisfied. Then:

- 1) $S_0(\lambda)$ is a meromorphic function;
- 2) $S_0(\lambda)$ has no poles and zeros on $\square^1$;
- 3) if $\lambda \in \square^1$, then $|S_0(\lambda)| = 1$;
- 4) $S_0(\lambda)$ has no poles on $\text{Im} \lambda > 0$;
- 5) if $\text{Im} \lambda \geq 0$, then $|S_0(\lambda)| \leq e^{2a\text{Im} \lambda}$;
- 6) if $\text{Im} \lambda \geq 0$, then

$$\left| \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)} \right| \leq 1, \quad \left| \frac{\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)} \right| \leq 1.$$

Proof. 1) the meromorphism of the function $S_0(\lambda)$ follows from the analyticity with respect λ to the entire plane $\square$ of the function $\psi(x, \lambda)$.

2) if the point $\lambda_0 \in \square^1$ is a pole (or zero) of the function $S_0(\lambda)$, then by virtue of reality $\psi(a, \lambda_0)$ we have $\psi_1(a, \lambda_0) = 0$, $\psi_2(a, \lambda_0) = 0$. According to the uniqueness theorem for the solution of the Cauchy problem $\psi(x, \lambda_0) \equiv 0$, which contradicts the fact that the solution $\psi(x, \lambda)$ is non-zero.

- 3) if $\lambda \in \square^1$, then

$$|S_0(\lambda)| = \left| e^{-2ia\lambda} \right| \cdot \left| \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda) + i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)} \right| = \frac{\sqrt{\psi_1^2(a, \lambda) + \psi_2^2(a, \lambda)}}{\sqrt{\psi_1^2(a, \lambda) + \psi_2^2(a, \lambda)}} = 1.$$

- 4) let's put

$$p_0(x) = \begin{cases} p(x), & x \leq a; \\ 0, & x > a, \end{cases} \quad q_0(x) = \begin{cases} q(x), & x \leq a; \\ 0, & x > a \end{cases}$$

and consider system (7) with coefficients $p_0(x)$, $q_0(x)$. Obviously, conditions (a) and (b) are satisfied for such a system. In this case

$$f^*(x, \lambda) = \begin{cases} e^{i\lambda a} \cdot \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{W(\lambda)} \cdot f(x, \lambda) - \\ - e^{i\lambda a} \cdot \frac{f_1(a, \lambda) - if_2(a, \lambda)}{W(\lambda)} \cdot \psi(x, \lambda), & x \leq a; \\ \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x}, & x > a \end{cases}$$

and

$$\psi^*(x, \lambda) = \begin{cases} \psi(x, \lambda), & x \leq a; \\ \begin{pmatrix} \cos \lambda(x-a) \\ \sin \lambda(x-a) \end{pmatrix} \cdot \psi_1(a, \lambda) + \\ + \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \lambda(x-a) \\ \cos \lambda(x-a) \end{pmatrix} \cdot \psi_2(a, \lambda), & x > a. \end{cases}$$

Let's assume that the function $S_0(\lambda)$ has a pole at a point λ_0 , where $\text{Im } \lambda_0 > 0$. Then the denominator $S_0(\lambda)$ vanishes, i.e. $\psi_1(a, \lambda_0) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda_0) = 0$. Then

$$\psi_2(a, \lambda_0) e^{-i\lambda_0 a} f^*(x, \lambda_0) = \psi^*(x, \lambda_0).$$

Hence it follows that $\psi^*(x, \lambda_0) \in L^2_2(-\infty, \infty)$, i.e. λ_0 ($\text{Im } \lambda_0 > 0$) – eigenvalue of problem (7) with potential $p_0(x)$ and $q_0(x)$. A contradiction, since the Dirac operator is symmetric.

Hence, $S_0(\lambda)$ has no poles in $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$.

5) consider an analytic function at $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$ and a function continuous on $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$

$$g(\lambda) = \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda) + i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}.$$

Using equality

$$m_-(\lambda) = - \frac{\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda)}$$

has

$$g(\lambda) = \frac{1 - im_-(\lambda)}{1 + im_-(\lambda)}.$$

From the asymptotic formula

$$m_-(\lambda) = -i + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right), \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \delta < \arg \lambda < \pi - \delta,$$

wherer $\delta > 0$ – any sufficiently small number, it follows that

$$g(\lambda) = \frac{1 - im_-(\lambda)}{1 + im_-(\lambda)} = \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right), \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \delta < \arg \lambda < \pi - \delta.$$

From the last representation, due to the arbitrariness $\delta > 0$ and equality $|g(\lambda)| = 1$ at $\text{Im } \lambda = 0$, we deduce the boundedness $g(\lambda)$ in $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$.

By virtue of the maximum principle for holomorphic functions [9], $|g(\lambda)|$ takes its greatest value at the boundary of the domain $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$, i.e. on $\text{Im } \lambda = 0$. Hence, $|g(\lambda)| \leq 1$ for $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$, more precisely $|g(\lambda)| < 1$ for $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$. By virtue of this inequality, from (15) we obtain $|S_0(\lambda)| \leq e^{2a \text{Im } \lambda}$.

6) similarly, considering the functions

$$g_1(\lambda) = \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}, \quad g_2(\lambda) = \frac{\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}$$

find

$$g_1(\lambda) = \frac{1}{1 + im_-(\lambda)} = \frac{1}{2 + \underline{O}(1/\lambda)} = \frac{1}{2} + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right),$$

$$|\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \delta < \arg \lambda < \pi - \delta,$$

$$g_2(\lambda) = \frac{-m_-(\lambda)}{1 + im_-(\lambda)} = \frac{i + \underline{O}(1/\lambda)}{2 + \underline{O}(1/\lambda)} = \frac{i}{2} + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right),$$

$$|\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \delta < \arg \lambda < \pi - \delta.$$

Using the maximum principle, we obtain $|g_1(\lambda)| \leq 1$, $|g_2(\lambda)| \leq 1$ at $\text{Im} \lambda \geq 0$. **Theorem 2 is proved.**

Theorem 3. If $\lambda \in \square^1$, then the asymptotics

$$S(\lambda) = S_0(\lambda) + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right), \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty.$$

Proof. Let us study the asymptotics of the function $W(\lambda)$ at $|\lambda| \rightarrow \infty$, $\text{Im} \lambda \geq 0$. Using asymptotics (11) for the Jost solution, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} W(\lambda) &= \begin{vmatrix} \psi_1(a, \lambda) & f_1(a, \lambda) \\ \psi_2(a, \lambda) & f_2(a, \lambda) \end{vmatrix} = \psi_1(a, \lambda) f_2(a, \lambda) - \psi_2(a, \lambda) f_1(a, \lambda) = \\ &= e^{i\lambda a} [\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)] \times \\ &\times \left\{ 1 + \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)} \cdot \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) - \frac{i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)} \cdot \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Using Theorem 2 from (16), we derive the following asymptotics

$$W(\lambda) = e^{i\lambda a} [\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)] \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right\}, \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \text{Im} \lambda \geq 0.$$

Hence, at $\lambda \in \square^1$ we get that

$$\overline{W(\lambda)} = e^{-i\lambda a} [\psi_1(a, \lambda) + i\psi_2(a, \lambda)] \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right\}, \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \text{Im} \lambda = 0.$$

So,

$$S(\lambda) = \frac{\overline{W(\lambda)}}{W(\lambda)} = e^{-2i\lambda a} \cdot \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda) + i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)} \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right\}, \quad \lambda \rightarrow \pm\infty.$$

Taking into account the boundedness $\lambda \in \square^1$ of the function $S_0(\lambda)$, we have

$$S(\lambda) = S_0(\lambda) + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right), \quad \lambda \rightarrow \pm\infty.$$

Theorem 3 is proved.

Lemma 6. The vector function $\frac{\psi(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x}}{W(\lambda)}$ for $x \geq a$ is uniformly bounded in $\text{Im} \lambda \geq 0$.

Proof. Let us first show that the vector function $\frac{\psi(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x}}{W(\lambda)}$ is bounded in the upper half-plane

$\text{Im} \lambda \geq 0$. For this we use the asymptotics

$$W(\lambda) = e^{i\lambda a} [\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)] \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right\}, \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \text{Im} \lambda \geq 0$$

and Theorem 2. Then

$$\left| \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda) e^{i\lambda a}}{W(\lambda)} \right| = \left| \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)} \right| \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right\} \leq \text{const},$$

likewise $\left| \frac{\psi_2(a, \lambda) e^{i\lambda a}}{W(\lambda)} \right| \leq \text{const.}$

Let now $x > a$. That

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\psi_1(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x}}{W(\lambda)} \right| &= \left| \frac{\psi_1(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x}}{e^{i\lambda a} [\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)] \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|\right)} \right\}} \right| = \\ &= \left| \frac{[\psi_1(x, \lambda)/\psi_1(a, \lambda)] \times e^{i\lambda(x-a)}}{1 - i [\psi_2(a, \lambda)/\psi_1(a, \lambda)]} \right| \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|\right)} \right\} = \\ &= \frac{\left| \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda)\theta_1(x, \lambda) - \psi_2(a, \lambda)\varphi_1(x, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda)} \right| \times |e^{i\lambda(x-a)}|}{|1 + im_-(\lambda)|} \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|\right)} \right\} = \\ &= \frac{\left| \theta_1(x, \lambda) - \frac{\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda)}\varphi_1(x, \lambda) \right|}{|1 + im_-(\lambda)|} \times |e^{i\lambda(x-a)}| \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|\right)} \right\} = \\ &= \frac{|\theta_1(x, \lambda) + m_-(\lambda)\varphi_1(x, \lambda)|}{|1 + im_-(\lambda)|} \times |e^{i\lambda(x-a)}| \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|\right)} \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

From the asymptotics

$$m_-(\lambda) = -i + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right), |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \delta < \arg \lambda < \pi - \delta \tag{18}$$

follows that

$$1 + im_-(\lambda) = 2 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right), |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \delta < \arg \lambda < \pi - \delta. \tag{19}$$

And using the asymptotics

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_1(x, \lambda) &= \cos \lambda(x-a) + \underline{O}\left(\frac{e^{(x-a)\text{Im}\lambda}}{|\lambda|}\right), \\ \varphi_1(x, \lambda) &= \sin \lambda(x-a) + \underline{O}\left(\frac{e^{(x-a)\text{Im}\lambda}}{|\lambda|}\right) \end{aligned}$$

find

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_1(x, \lambda) + m(\lambda)\varphi_1(x, \lambda) &= \cos \lambda(x-a) + \underline{O}\left(\frac{e^{(x-a)\text{Im}\lambda}}{|\lambda|}\right) + \\ &+ \left\{ -i + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right) \right\} \cdot \left\{ \sin \lambda(x-a) + \underline{O}\left(\frac{e^{(x-a)\text{Im}\lambda}}{|\lambda|}\right) \right\} = \\ &= \cos \lambda(x-a) - i \sin \lambda(x-a) + \underline{O}\left(\frac{e^{(x-a)\text{Im}\lambda}}{|\lambda|}\right). \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Substituting (19) and (20) into (17), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\psi_1(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x}}{W(\lambda)} \right| &= \frac{|1 + \underline{O}(1/|\lambda|)|}{2 + \underline{O}(1/|\lambda|)} \cdot \left\{ 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right\} = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right), \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \delta < \arg \lambda < \pi - \delta. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Let now $x > a$ and $\lambda \in \square^1$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{2i\psi_1(x, \lambda)}{W(\lambda)} \right| &= \left| S(\lambda) f_1(x, \lambda) - \overline{f_1(x, \lambda)} \right| = \\ &= \left| S(\lambda) i e^{i\lambda x} \left(1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right) + i e^{-i\lambda x} \left(1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right) \right| \leq \\ &\leq 1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

From (21) and (22), due to the arbitrariness $\delta > 0$, we have $\left| \frac{2i\psi_1(x, \lambda)}{W(\lambda)} \right| \leq \text{const.}$

Likewise $\left| \frac{2i\psi_2(x, \lambda)}{W(\lambda)} \right| \leq \text{const.}$ **Lemma 6 is proved.**

Further, by the method of V.A. Marchenko, a linear integral equation is derived for $A(x, t)$ - the kernel of the representation (10)

$$f(x, \lambda) = \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x} + \int_x^\infty A(x, t) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda t} dt.$$

Theorem 4. For each fixed $x \in \square^1$ function $A(x, t)$ - the core of representation (10) satisfies the Gelfand-Levitan-Marchenko integral equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} G(x+y) + \int_x^\infty A(x, t) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} G(t+y) dt - A(x, y) \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 0, \quad (x < y < \infty), \quad (23)$$

where

$$G(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty [S(\lambda) - S_0(\lambda)] e^{i\lambda t} d\lambda. \quad (24)$$

Proof. To derive integral equation (23), equality (14)

$$u(x, \lambda) = S(\lambda) f(x, \lambda) - \overline{f(x, \lambda)}$$

rewrite in the form

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, \lambda) - S_0(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x} + \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{-i\lambda x} &= \\ &= [S(\lambda) - S_0(\lambda)] f(x, \lambda) + S_0(\lambda) \left[f(x, \lambda) - \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x} \right] - \\ &- \left[\overline{f(x, \lambda)} - \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{-i\lambda x} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Substituting expression (10) into (25) we have:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ u(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x} - S_0(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{2i\lambda x} + \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\} e^{-i\lambda x} = \\ & = [S(\lambda) - S_0(\lambda)] \cdot \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x} + [S(\lambda) - S_0(\lambda)] \cdot \int_x^\infty A(x, t) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda t} dt + \\ & + \int_x^\infty A(x, t) S_0(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda t} dt - \int_x^\infty A(x, t) \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{-i\lambda t} dt. \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

Let us multiply both sides of equality (26) by $\frac{1}{2\pi} e^{i\lambda y}$ ($x < y$), and integrate the resulting equality with respect to λ on the interval $(-\infty, \infty)$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty \left\{ u(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x} - S_0(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{2i\lambda x} + \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\} e^{i\lambda(y-x)} d\lambda = \\ & = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty [S(\lambda) - S_0(\lambda)] \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda(x+y)} d\lambda + \\ & + \int_x^\infty A(x, t) \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty [S(\lambda) - S_0(\lambda)] \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda(t+y)} d\lambda \right\} dt + \\ & + \int_x^\infty A(x, t) \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty S_0(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda(t+y)} d\lambda \right\} dt - \\ & - \int_x^\infty A(x, t) \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda(y-t)} d\lambda \right\} dt. \end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

Let's introduce the following function

$$F(\lambda) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ u(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x} - S_0(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{2i\lambda x} + \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}. \tag{28}$$

Let us show that the function $F(\lambda)$ uniformly bounded in a half-plane $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$ as $x \geq a$. Lemma 6 implies uniform boundedness in $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$ the function

$$\frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ u(x, \lambda) e^{i\lambda x} + \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\}.$$

It is easy to see that

$$\left| S_0(\lambda) e^{2i\lambda x} \right| = \left| e^{2i\lambda(x-a)} \cdot \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda) + i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)} \right| \leq e^{-2(x-a)\text{Im } \lambda} \leq 1.$$

Hence, $F(\lambda)$ is uniformly bounded in $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$ at $x \geq a$.

Now consider the function $F(\lambda)$ for $\lambda \in \square^1$:

$$F(\lambda) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ [S(\lambda) f(x, \lambda) - \overline{f(x, \lambda)}] e^{i\lambda x} - S_0(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{2i\lambda x} + \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \right\} =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ S(\lambda) f(x, \lambda) - S_0(\lambda) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{i\lambda x} \right\} e^{i\lambda x} - \\
&- \frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ \overline{f(x, \lambda)} - \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{-i\lambda x} \right\} e^{i\lambda x} = \\
&= \frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ S(\lambda) \left[1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right] - S_0(\lambda) \right\} \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} e^{2i\lambda x} - \\
&- \frac{1}{2\pi} \left\{ \left[1 + \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right) \right] - 1 \right\} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right).
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the function $\lambda F(\lambda)$ is bounded on the entire line and $\lambda F(\lambda) = \underline{O}(1)$, $|\lambda| \rightarrow \infty$, $\text{Im } \lambda > 0$.

By virtue of the Phragmen–Lindelöf theorem ([8], p. 357), $\lambda F(\lambda)$ it is also bounded in $\text{Im } \lambda \geq 0$. This implies that uniformly for $x \in [a, +\infty)$, we have the estimate

$$F(\lambda) = \underline{O}\left(\frac{1}{|\lambda|}\right), \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty, \quad \text{Im } \lambda \geq 0.$$

Let's take a contour $\gamma_R = I_R \cup C_R^+$, where $I_R = [-R, R]$ and C_R^+ semicircle of radius R on the upper half-plane with a diameter $I_R = [-R, R]$. By virtue of the Cauchy residue theorem, we have

$$\int_{I_R} F(\lambda) e^{i\lambda(y-x)} d\lambda + \int_{C_R^+} F(\lambda) e^{i\lambda(y-x)} d\lambda = 0. \quad (29)$$

Using the Jordan lemma from (29), we obtain

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(\lambda) e^{i\lambda(y-x)} d\lambda = 0. \quad (30)$$

Taking into account the identity $\frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i\lambda(y-t)} d\lambda = \delta(y-t)$, equality (30) and designations (24),

(28), we rewrite identity (27) in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} G(x+y) + \int_x^{\infty} A(x,t) \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} G(t+y) dt + \\
&+ \int_x^{\infty} A(x,t) \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S_0(\lambda) e^{i\lambda(t+y)} d\lambda \right\} dt - A(x,y) \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 0.
\end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Lemma 7. For $t + y - 2a > 0$, we have the equality

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S_0(\lambda) e^{i\lambda(t+y)} d\lambda = 0. \quad (32)$$

Proof. We integrate $g(\lambda)e^{i\lambda(t+y-2a)}$ along the contour (fig. 1)

fig. 1
where

$$g(\lambda) = \frac{\psi_1(a, \lambda) + i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda) - i\psi_2(a, \lambda)}, \quad t + y - 2a > 0.$$

Then from the Cauchy residue theorem we find

$$\int_{C_{R, \epsilon}^+} g(\lambda)e^{i\lambda(t+y-2a)} d\lambda + \int_{-\sqrt{R^2 - \epsilon^2} + i\epsilon}^{\sqrt{R^2 - \epsilon^2} + i\epsilon} g(\lambda)e^{i\lambda(t+y-2a)} d\lambda = 0. \tag{33}$$

Since at

$$\delta < \arg \lambda < \pi - \delta \quad \left(\delta = \arcsin \frac{\epsilon}{R} \right), \quad |\lambda| \rightarrow \infty$$

the asymptotics

$$g(\lambda) = \frac{1 - im_-(\lambda)}{1 + im_-(\lambda)} = O\left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right),$$

then using the Jordan lemma, we have:

$$\int_{C_{R, \epsilon}^+} g(\lambda)e^{i\lambda(t+y-2a)} d\lambda \rightarrow 0, \text{ at } R \rightarrow \infty.$$

Passing to the limit at $R \rightarrow \infty$ and $\epsilon \rightarrow +0$ in equality (33), we find

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(\lambda)e^{i\lambda(t+y-2a)} d\lambda = 0.$$

Hence, equality (32) is satisfied. **Lemma 7 is proved.**

Using equality (31) and (32), we derive the Gelfand–Levitan–Marchenko integral equation (23).

Equation (23) is equivalent to a system of four integral equations with real coefficients:

$$\begin{aligned} & \begin{pmatrix} iG(x+y) \\ G(x+y) \end{pmatrix} + \int_x^\infty \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}(x,t) & A_{12}(x,t) \\ A_{21}(x,t) & A_{22}(x,t) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} G(t+y) dt - \\ & - \begin{pmatrix} A_{11}(x,y) & A_{12}(x,y) \\ A_{21}(x,y) & A_{22}(x,y) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} -i \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 0, \\ & \begin{pmatrix} iG(x+y) \\ G(x+y) \end{pmatrix} + \int_x^\infty \begin{pmatrix} iA_{11}(x,t) + A_{12}(x,t) \\ iA_{21}(x,t) + A_{22}(x,t) \end{pmatrix} G(t+y) dt + \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \begin{pmatrix} iA_{11}(x, y) - A_{12}(x, y) \\ iA_{21}(x, y) - A_{22}(x, y) \end{pmatrix} = 0,$$

$$\begin{cases} iG(x+y) + \int_x^\infty [iA_{11}(x, t) + A_{12}(x, t)]G(t+y)dt + iA_{11}(x, y) - A_{12}(x, y) = 0 \\ G(x+y) + \int_x^\infty [iA_{21}(x, t) + A_{22}(x, t)]G(t+y)dt + iA_{21}(x, y) - A_{22}(x, y) = 0, \end{cases}$$

Let $G(x) = G_1(x) + iG_2(x)$, where $G_1(x)$ and $G_2(x)$ are real functions. Then

$$iG_1(x+y) - G_2(x+y) + iA_{11}(x, y) - A_{12}(x, y) +$$

$$+ \int_x^\infty \{A_{11}(x, t)[iG_1(t+y) - G_2(t+y)] + A_{12}(x, t)[G_1(t+y) + iG_2(t+y)]\}dt = 0,$$

$$G_1(x+y) + iG_2(x+y) + iA_{21}(x, y) - A_{22}(x, y) +$$

$$+ \int_x^\infty \{A_{21}(x, t)[iG_1(t+y) - G_2(t+y)] + A_{22}(x, t)[G_1(t+y) + iG_2(t+y)]\}dt = 0,$$

i.e.

$$G_1(x+y) + A_{11}(x, y) + \int_x^\infty \{A_{11}(x, t)G_1(t+y) + A_{12}(x, t)G_2(t+y)\}dt = 0,$$

$$G_2(x+y) + A_{12}(x, y) + \int_x^\infty \{A_{11}(x, t)G_2(t+y) - A_{12}(x, t)G_1(t+y)\}dt = 0,$$

$$-G_1(x+y) + A_{22}(x, y) + \int_x^\infty \{A_{21}(x, t)G_2(t+y) - A_{22}(x, t)G_1(t+y)\}dt = 0,$$

$$G_2(x+y) + A_{21}(x, y) + \int_x^\infty \{A_{21}(x, t)G_1(t+y) + A_{22}(x, t)G_2(t+y)\}dt = 0.$$

Equation (23) plays an important role in solving the inverse problem of scattering theory. The kernel $G(t)$ of the integral equation (23) is expressed directly in terms of the scattering function $S(\lambda)$ by formula (24). Therefore, having solved the integral equation (23), we restore $A(x, t)$ and, by virtue of the equality $\Omega(x) = BA(x, x) - A(x, x)B$, construct a potential matrix-function $\Omega(x)$ for $x \geq a$.

Finally, we present a method for finding the potential matrix-function $\Omega(x)$ for $x \leq a$. Consider problem (6). As has been proven

$$m_-(\lambda) = \frac{a_1(\lambda)}{a_2(\lambda)} \text{ and } \psi(a, \lambda) = \begin{pmatrix} a_2(\lambda) \\ -a_1(\lambda) \end{pmatrix}.$$

Hence we get that

$$m_-(\lambda) = -\frac{\psi_2(a, \lambda)}{\psi_1(a, \lambda)}. \quad (34)$$

Using decomposition

$$\frac{2i}{W(\lambda)} \psi(a, \lambda) = S(\lambda) f(a, \lambda) - \overline{f(a, \lambda)}, \quad \lambda \in \square^1,$$

we rewrite formula (34) in the form

$$m_-(\lambda) = -\frac{S(\lambda)f_2(a, \lambda) - \overline{f_2(a, \lambda)}}{S(\lambda)f_1(a, \lambda) - \overline{f_1(a, \lambda)}}, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^1. \tag{35}$$

It is required to indicate a procedure for restoring problem (6) from a given Weyl–Titchmarsh function (35). To do this, we reduce problem (6) to a problem of the following form

$$\begin{cases} B \frac{dz}{dt} + \tilde{\Omega}(t)z = \mu z, & 0 \leq t < \infty \\ z_1(0) = 0. \end{cases} \tag{36}$$

To this end, in problem (6) we make the replacement $x = -t + a$. Then problem (6) takes the form

$$\begin{cases} B \left(-\frac{dy}{dt} \right) + \Omega(-t + a)y = \lambda y, & -\infty \leq -t + a \leq a \\ y_1|_{t=0} = 0 \end{cases}$$

i.e.

$$\begin{cases} B \frac{dy}{dt} + (-\Omega(a - t))y = (-\lambda)y, & 0 \leq t < \infty \\ y_1|_{t=0} = 0. \end{cases} \tag{37}$$

For convenience, we introduce the notation

$$z(t) = y(a - t), \quad \tilde{\Omega}(t) = -\Omega(a - t), \quad \mu = -\lambda. \tag{38}$$

Then problem (37) takes the form (36). In this case the solution $\psi(x, \lambda) \in L^2_2(-\infty, a)$ will go to

$$\tilde{\psi}(t, \mu) = \psi(a - t, -\mu) \in L^2_2(0, \infty).$$

Really,

$$\int_{-\infty}^a [\psi_1^2(x, \lambda) + \psi_2^2(x, \lambda)] dx < \infty,$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} [\psi_1^2(a - t, \mu) + \psi_2^2(a - t, \mu)](-dt) < \infty,$$

i.e.

$$\int_0^{\infty} [\tilde{\psi}_1^2(t, \mu) + \tilde{\psi}_2^2(t, \mu)] dt < \infty.$$

If $\tilde{\theta}(t, \mu) = \theta(a - t, -\mu)$, $\tilde{\varphi}(t, \mu) = \varphi(a - t, -\mu)$, that

$$\tilde{\theta}(0, \mu) = \theta(a, -\mu) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \tilde{\varphi}(0, \mu) = \varphi(a, -\mu) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Because $\tilde{\psi}(t, \mu) = C(\mu)[\tilde{\theta}(t, \mu) + \tilde{m}(\mu)\tilde{\varphi}(t, \mu)]$, that

$$\tilde{\psi}(0, \mu) = C(\mu) \left[\begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} + \tilde{m}(\mu) \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \right] = \begin{pmatrix} C(\mu) \\ -C(\mu)\tilde{m}(\mu) \end{pmatrix},$$

from here

$$\tilde{m}(\mu) = -\frac{\tilde{\psi}_2(0, \mu)}{\tilde{\psi}_1(0, \mu)}. \tag{39}$$

Due to (39) and (34) we have

$$\tilde{m}(\mu) = -\frac{\psi_2(a, -\mu)}{\psi_1(a, -\mu)} = m_-(-\mu).$$

Now, knowing the Weil–Titchmarsh function $\tilde{m}(\mu)$ of problem (36), we find the spectral function $\tilde{\rho}(\mu)$. To do this, we find the poles μ_n , $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ of the function $\tilde{m}(\mu)$ and the residues $r_n = \operatorname{res}_{\mu_n} \tilde{m}(\mu)$ at these poles. Then

$$\tilde{\rho}(\mu) = \begin{cases} -\sum_{\mu < \mu_n \leq 0} r_n, & \mu \leq 0, \\ \sum_{0 \leq \mu_n < \mu} r_n, & \mu > 0. \end{cases}$$

Using the Gelfand–Levitan procedure, to $\tilde{\rho}(\mu)$ we restore the matrix–function from $\tilde{\Omega}(t)$ [7, pp. 403–422]. In this case, the conditions given in Theorem 3.1 are imposed on the function. [7, pp. 412–413]. Let's put

$$\Phi(t, s) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1 - \cos \mu t}{\mu} \\ -\frac{\sin \mu t}{\mu} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1 - \cos \mu s}{\mu} & -\frac{\sin \mu s}{\mu} \end{pmatrix} d\left(\tilde{\rho}(\mu) - \frac{1}{\pi} \mu\right),$$

$$F(t, s) = \frac{\partial^2 \Phi(t, s)}{\partial t \partial s},$$

and solve the Gelfand–Levitan integral equation

$$F(t, s) + K(t, s) + \int_0^t K(t, z)F(z, s)dz = 0, \quad (0 \leq s \leq t)$$

with respect to the matrix $K(t, s) = (K_{ij}(t, s))_{i, j=1, 2}$. Then, according to the formula

$$\tilde{\Omega}(t) = K(t, t)B - BK(t, t)$$

find $\tilde{\Omega}(t)$, at $t \geq 0$. Then it follows from equality (38) that $\Omega(x) = -\tilde{\Omega}(a - x)$, where $x \leq a$.

CONCLUSION

The present work is devoted to the study of the inverse problem with respect to the scattering theory function and with respect to the spectral function for the Dirac operator on the entire line and on the half-line. The results obtained can be used in the spectral theory of linear operators, in mathematical physics when integrating nonlinear equations, as well as in quantum mechanics and in other areas of natural science.

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